

ON OPTIMUM ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED PLATES UNDER SHEAR*

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Let us consider the optimization problem of bidirection reinforced laminated plates under shear as the same problem in Ref.1. It is assumed that, the laminate is composed of N layers and each layer of the plate has the same thickness h and an equal number of the same fiber in the θ_k and $-\theta_k$ direction with respect to the x axis (subscript k shows the k-th layer). Taking $R=a/b$ which represents the length-to-width ratio of plate. For the plate of simply supported edges S_2 , the deflections is assumed as

$$\begin{aligned} U &= \sum \sum U_{mn} \cos(m\pi x/a) \sin(n\pi y/b) \\ V &= \sum \sum V_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/a) \cos(n\pi y/b) \quad (m=1,2,\dots, m_1, n=1,2,\dots, n_1) \\ W &= \sum \sum W_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/a) \sin(n\pi y/b) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

the buckling differential equations of laminated plates under shear with the Galerkin method can be written as following

$$\begin{aligned} [T_{33} - T_C] W_{pq} - \lambda \sum_m \sum_n \frac{mnpq}{(m^2-p^2)(n^2-q^2)} W_{mn} = 0 \\ (p=1,2,\dots,m_1 \text{ and } q=1,2,\dots,n_1) (m+p \text{ and } n+q \text{ are odd}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where p and q are the number of half waves in the x and y directions, respectively, and

$$\lambda = \frac{32abR^2}{\pi^4} N_{xy} \quad (3)$$

$$T_C = \frac{T_{11}T_{23}^2 + T_{22}T_{13}^2 - 2T_{12}T_{13}T_{23}}{T_{11}T_{22} - T_{12}^2} \quad (4)$$

$$T_{11} = A_{11}p^2 + A_{66}q^2R^2, \quad T_{22} = A_{66}p^2 + A_{22}q^2R^2, \quad T_{12} = (A_{12} + A_{66})pqR,$$

$$T_{13} = B_{11}p^3 + (B_{12} + 2B_{66})pq^2R^2, \quad T_{23} = (B_{12} + 2B_{66})p^2qR + B_{22}q^3R^3 \quad (5)$$

$$T_{33} = D_{11}p^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})p^2q^2R^2 + D_{22}q^4R^4$$

where the A_{ij} , B_{ij} and D_{ij} are extensional, coupling and bending stiffnesses of laminate, respectively.

Taking the N angles of all layers as design variables and the λ as the object function to find the maximum value of the λ , This is an unconstrained optimum problem and was used in Refs.1,2. However, it will be proved that, this problem can be simplified.

The equations (2) can be rewritten using matrix notation

$$[K-C] \{W\} - \lambda [G] \{W\} = 0 \quad (6)$$

in which, the elements of $[G]$ and diagonal matrices $[K]$, $[C]$ are:

$$K_{ii} = T_{33}, \quad C_{ii} = T_C, \quad G_{ii} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$G_{il} = \frac{mnpq}{(m^2 - p^2)(n^2 - q^2)} \quad (\text{when } m+p \text{ and } n+q \text{ are odd}) \quad (8)$$

$$G_{il} = 0 \quad (\text{when } m+p \text{ or } n+q \text{ is even})$$

the minimum eigenvalue of equation (6) is given by Rayleigh Quotient

$$\lambda_1 = \min \frac{\{W\}^T [K+C] \{W\}}{\{W\}^T [G] \{W\}} \quad (9)$$

let

$$\beta_1 = \min \frac{\{W\}^T [K] \{W\}}{\{W\}^T [G] \{W\}} \quad \mu_1 = \min \frac{\{W\}^T [C] \{W\}}{\{W\}^T [G] \{W\}} \quad (10)$$

In Ref.3, it was proved that, both the T_{33} and T_C must be positive, i.e. the $[K]$ and $[C]$ all are positive definite matrices. For the generalized eigenvalue problem, as for normal eigenvalue problem⁶, we can prove that

$$\beta_1 \geq \mu_1 + \lambda_1 \quad (11)$$

thus

$$\beta_1 \geq \lambda_1 \quad (12)$$

It represents that, the effect of coupling stiffness, i.e. the effect of $[C]$ must reduce the shear buckling load of laminate. In addition, in Ref.3, it has been proved that, for any nonsymmetric laminate must have a corresponding symmetric laminate making that, the both nonsymmetric and symmetric laminates have the same T_{33} , i.e. have the same β_1 in expression (11). Because of the T_C is zero for symmetric laminate, so we can conclude that, for any nonsymmetric laminate under shear, there must have a symmetric laminate which has higher buckling load than that nonsymmetric laminate, i.e. the optimum laminate with maximum value of buckling load must be a symmetric one.

For symmetric laminate, the expression (6) can be simplified as

$$[K] \{W\} - \lambda [G] \{W\} = 0 \quad (13)$$

Taking the derivative of Eq. (13) with respect to θ_k and, for finding the extremum of λ , let the derivative equal to zero, we obtain

$$\{W\}^T \frac{\partial [K]}{\partial \theta_k} \{W\} = 0 \quad (k=1, 2, \dots, N/2) \quad (14)$$

From Eq. (14), the optimum ply angles can be gotten. let

$$J = U_2(p^4 - q^4 R^4), \quad F = U_3(6p^2 q^2 R^2 - p^4 - q^4 R^4) \quad (15)$$

in which, the U_2, U_3 are invariances of stiffness. The derivative of T with respect to θ_k , i.e. the elements of diagonal matrix $(\partial[K])/(\partial\theta_k)$ are

$$\frac{\partial T_{33}}{\partial \theta_k} = \frac{4}{3}(Z_k^3 - Z_{k-1}^3) \sin 2\theta_k (4F \cos 2\theta_k - J) \quad (16)$$

Substituting the Eq.(16) into Eq.(14), it can be seen, there are $N/2$ Eqs. and which have the same form and contain only one unknown variable θ_k in each equation, so we can get the same values of θ_k from these equations. It is easy to know, the roots of Eq.(14) can not more than three, containing the 0° and 90° .

For example, Taking the laminate same as that in Ref.1 the number of layers $N=6$, and the $m_1=n_1=4$, the objective function $\phi=10^5/\lambda$. Because of the laminated plate, which have the optimum ply orientation under shear load, must be symmetrical, so we can only use the symmetric laminate for optimum analysis. The numerical results of calculation are given in Tab.1, The Powell method are used for optimization. The results quoted from Ref.2 are given in Tab.3. The results in Tab.1 are quite agree with the results in Tab.3. but it is only analysis for symmetric laminate, so not only the equations of calculation can be simplified, but also the number of design variable can be reduced to one half. It has proved that, as mentioned before, for any number of laminae in an laminated plate, the number of different optimum ply angles no more than three, including 0° and 90° , and the another angle, between 0° and 90° , must be equal each other. It can be seen, the values of optimum ply angle of each lamina in Tab. 1 or Tab.3 are very close each other and that values increase with the R . if the R of two plates are reciprocal each other, the optimum ply angles of the two plates are complement each other. Thus, we can let the ply angles of each layer be all equal each other, i.e. the optimization analysis as mentioned before can be simplified as an analysis of single design variable. Calculating the same example, as mentioned before, with the single design variable. The result of calculation are given in Tab.2. It can be seen, they are all agree with those in Tab.1.

Table 1 Optimum Fiber Direction (Deg.)

R	θ_1	θ_2	θ_3	ϕ
0.5	32.67	32.98	32.77	2.826
0.8	40.13	40.13	40.13	1.477
1.0	45	45	44.95	0.980
1.5	54.26	54.26	54.27	0.387
2.0	57.35	57.08	57	0.177
4.0	80.64	80.5	81.21	0.021
5.0	90	89.87	89.81	0.009

Table 2

R	θ	ϕ
0.5	32.76	2.826
0.8	40.11	1.477
1.0	45.03	0.980
1.5	54.24	0.387
2.0	57.25	0.177
4.0	80.53	0.0205
5.0	89.97	0.0087

Table 3 Optimum Fiber Direction for Laminated Plates (Deg.)

R	θ_1	θ_2	θ_3	θ_4	θ_5	θ_6	ϕ
0.5	32	33	33.6	33.6	33	32	2.8
0.8	40.1	40.1	40.1	40.1	40.1	40.1	1.495
1.0	45	45	45	45	45	45	0.992
1.5	54	54.6	54.6	54.1	54	54	0.307
2.0	58.6	59.7	60.4	60.4	59.7	58.6	0.177

As already discussed, we obtain.

1. The optimum structure of laminated plates under shear for buckling load must be symmetric laminate, the number of different optimum ply angles, including 0° and 90° , is no more than three.
2. The optimization analysis, mentioned before, can be simplified to single variable optimization.
3. As the length-to-width ratio R of plate increases, both the optimum ply angle and the buckling load increase.
4. If exchange the length a and width b , i.e. the length-to-width ratio of two plates

are reciprocal each other, the optimum ply angles of the two plate are complement and the buckling loads are equal each other.

REFERENCES

1. Y.Hirano, J.Composite Materials, 13, (1979), 329-334.
2. Jiang Yongqiu, Computational Structural Mechanics and Applications, 1(1), 1984, 39-46, (in Chinese).
3. Tang Jun, Computational Structural Mechanics and Applications, 1(2), 1984, 75-84. (in Chinese).
4. Tang Jun, Acta Mechanica Sinica, 19, 1987, Supplementary Issue, 268-272.
5. Jones, R.M., Mechanics of Composite Materials, McGRAW-HILL Book Company, 1975.
6. Chao Zhihao, Zhang Yude, Li Ruixia, Calculation of Matrix and Equation Roots, (in Chinese). Education Publication House, 1984.